

Auranofin and Baicalin Inhibit *Clostridioides difficile* Growth and Sporulation: An *In vitro* Study

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Table 1: Viable cell count in CFU/mL in control plates compared to drugs plates

Duration	Control	Auranofin	Baicalin	Vancomycin	P- value
	Mean (SD)x 10 ⁶				
24 hours	1.41(0.97)	0.05(0.03)	0.06(0.06)	0.1(0.08)	<0.004
48 hours	4.59(0.72)	0.12(0.05)	0.21(0.09)	0.22(0.05)	<0.001

Table 2: Viable spore count in CFU/mL in control plates compared to drugs plates

Duration	Control	Auranofin	Baicalin	Vancomycin	P- value
	Mean (SD)x 10 ⁶				
24 hours	1.0(0.49)	0.18(0.22)	0.27(0.3)	0.37(0.42)	0.035
48 hours	1.2(0.85)	0.09(0.04)	0.15(0.1)	0.6(0.16)	0.013

Table 3: Amount of toxin in control tube compared to drug tubes

	Control	Auranofin	Baicalin	Vancomycin	P- value
	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	Mean (SD)	
Amount of toxin	5381.8(3889)	116.6(23.8)	6097.3(3943)	5062.7(4154)	0.035

	Control	Auranofin	Baicalin	Vancomycin	P- value
	Mean (SD)x 10 ³	Mean (SD)x 10 ³	Mean (SD)x 10 ³	Mean (SD) x 10 ³	
Amount of toxin	5.38(3.9)	0.12(0.02)	6.10(3.9)	5.06(4.2)	0.035